

A Brucite and gibbsite

- Tetrahedral cation
- Octahedral cation
- ⊙ Interlayer cation (K^+, Na^+)
- Exchangeable cation

- Oxygen
- ⊙ Hydroxyl group (OH^-)
- Water molecule
- ⊖ Oxygen + hydroxyl (in projection)